

Impact of Environmental Costs on the Value of Listed Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria

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¹Zephaniah Liuraman & ²Ipeyen Dan-Musa

¹Department of Accounting, Nigerian Army University Biu, Borno State, Nigeria

²Department of Accounting and Finance, Taraba State Polytechnic, Suntai

Email: ¹zliuraman@gmail.com, ²ipeyenmusa@gmail.com

Abstract

This study examined the impact of environmental costs on the value of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. A correlation research design was adopted, while the target population was manufacturing companies listed on the main board of the Nigerian Exchange Group as of 31st December 2023. Out of the 43 companies, 16 were selected based on the criteria that, the company must have been listed on or before 31st December 2013 and remained listed till 31st December 2023, and also have complete annual reports and accounts over the period of the study (2014-2023). Panel regression analysis was used to analyze the data collected. The results of the analysis show that; ecological management cost, employees' health and safety cost, and gas emission management cost have positive and significant impact on Tobin's Q ratio of the companies. While waste management costs have a negative significant impact on Tobin's Q ratio of the companies. The study therefore concludes that environmental costs have a positive and significant impact on the value of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. This signifies that improvements in ecological management, employee health and safety, and gas emission management would significantly improve the value of manufacturing companies through an increase in firms' share prices. Therefore, the management of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria should pay adequate attention to policies such as employees' health insurance, funding ecological management, and installations of equipment for gas and waste collection and disposal. These policies would help management to gain legitimacy, hence improving the firm's value.

Keywords: Environmental costs, Firms' value, Listed manufacturing companies, Nigeria.

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Introduction

Maximization of owners' wealth is the main objective of any profit-making business. Increasing firms' value is crucial to investors given the current economic challenges across the globe. Firm value is a description of certain conditions that the company wants to achieve as a form of public trust in the company for all activities carried out by the company. It consists of the nominal value, market value, intrinsic value, and book value. However, the economic challenges have a tremendous effect on business strategies make the market so dynamic and increase business competition and risk (Temitope, 2021). Capital base and managerial skills that were conventionally considered to be the major driving force for business growth through an increase in business value (Rita, 2022) are eroding in their influence. Studies such as Eric and Jacob (2022) and Eke *et al.* (2024) emphasized that, for a business to remain sustainable in recent business development, capital base and managerial skill are not the only major factors, but the mood of business operation and its legitimacy also have a tremendous impact on business success. Hence, both governments and investors are clamouring for environmental consciousness by businesses, since businesses are seen seriously polluting their

operating environment. On this note, firms such as manufacturing companies in Nigeria are categorized as environmentally sensitive industries which contribute a lot to polluting the environment. Therefore, to mitigate this negative impact of business activities on the environment, various laws and regulations were enacted in Nigeria. With these laws and regulations, companies are expected to be conscientious and exhibit a high sense of responsibility by mitigating the negative impact of their operating activities on the environment and society at large. However, these environmental preservation activities are seen as a cost without benefit to many organizations (Ilelaboye & Alade, 2022), thus, the management of firms pay little or no attention to environmental preservation activities. Environmental costs are the aggregate of the monetary value of resources sacrificed or intended to be sacrificed for the preservation of the environment. It consists of prevention cost, planning cost, disposal cost, control cost, and repair cost.

In this regard, studies were conducted to observe the effect of environmental costs on firms' value. However, there is still a paucity of empirical evidence, particularly in developing countries such as Nigeria as recommended by Aliamutu *et al.* (2022). Furthermore, apart from the concentration of

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the previous studies in the oil and gas sector, the results of the previous studies were contradictory and inconsistent, hence inconclusive (Okore, 2021). Studies such as Zhenjea and Jian (2019) in China, and Aliamutu *et al.* (2023) in South Africa reported positive and significant effects of environmental costs on financial performance. But Dinniyah and Nuzula (2019) in Japan, and Husnah and Ayunita (2021) in Indonesia documented a negative effect of environmental costs on profitability. While Pandey and Kumar (2016) in India, and Nuzula (2019) in Japan reported no significant relationship between environmental costs and profitability. More so, the few studies conducted in Nigeria such as Okezie *et al.* (2019), Onuora and Chiedu (2019), and Oraka (2021), apart from being concentrated in the oil and gas sector, also reported inconsistent findings of the effect of environmental costs on financial performance and they were cross-sectional covering at maximum two years. In addition, most of the studies used only one to two proxies of environmental cost. Hence, the motivation of this study is to examine the impact of environmental costs on the firms' value of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria over a period of ten years (2014-2023) using four major proxies of environmental cost such as waste management cost, ecological management cost, employee health and safety cost, and gas emission management cost.

To achieve these objectives, the following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study.

H₀₁: Waste management costs have no significant impact on firms' value of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

H₀₂: Employee health and safety cost has no significant impact on firms' value of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

H₀₃: Ecological management cost has no significant impact on firms' value of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

H₀₄: Gas emission management cost has no significant impact on firms' value of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria

The novelty of this study is in its contributions to knowledge in the area of environmental accounting and firms' value. Therefore, the study would benefit management, regulatory agencies and other stakeholders of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. It would enlighten the management of the companies on the influence of corporate environmental activities on long-term sustainability.

Literature Review

Firms' Value

A firm's value is the result of the management process related to corporate goals. It is a product of the activities and

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return on investment in a given period (Ousama *et al.*, 2019). The value of the company is the investors' perception of the firm's success rate commonly reflected in the firm's share price. The share price of a firm indicates the result of the investment activities of the business, thus creating signals to the public in relation to business value to enhance investors' economic decision-making (Reschiwati *et al.*, 2020). This firm value is mostly measured using Tobin's Q. Tobin's Q ratio indicates the current financial market estimates of the value of returns of every incremental investment. The ratio composes of firms' liabilities, inventory, equity, and company's assets. Hence, the higher the value of Tobin's Q indicates the future growth prospect of the firm. This increasing value of the company can attract investors to invest their capital. This can happen because the greater the market value of a company's assets compared to the company's asset book value, the greater the investor is willing to spend more to own shares of the company. Therefore, for the purpose of this study, Tobin's Q ratio was used to measure firms' value of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Environmental Costs

The concept of environmental costs was defined by KPMG (2012) as costs incurred by an organization to prevent, monitor, and control environmental impact. These are expenses related to the development,

identification, remediation, and prevention of environmental damage. With the growing importance of environmental issues in the business world, firms are required to be conscious of their operating environment since they are partners in development and contribute to negative environmental impacts. Hence, firms are expected to play a leading role in instituting measures to mitigate their environmental impacts and achieve a global reduction in the negativities of their actions. In the course of doing this, amount of resources is sacrificed by firms to achieve a clean environment as well as maximize profit. Thus, environmental costs are the amount of money spent by a company to prevent, protect, monitor, and control environmental impact. The money spent could be for waste management and control, improving employees' health and safety, ecological management, and the control of gas emissions (Oloff & Vandermerve 2017; Ubesie *et al.*, 2022).

Waste is anything that cannot be turned into a marketable product and is therefore indicative of production inefficiency (Okore, 2021). Waste generation and waste management are critical environmental issues faced by countries all over the world. Recovery, collection, and removal of waste, which includes the administration of such an operation, is useful for waste management. Thus Jasch, (2006) defined waste management cost as the costs of wasted materials and other costs related to their

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processing such as the costs of energy, transportation, and labour. It also includes investment in waste treatment facilities and the cost of untreated waste outflows.

Ecological management is aimed at environmental protection (Falope & Udeh, 2019). Thus, Chiamogu and Okoye (2020) described environmental protection as the practice of protecting the natural environment by individuals, organizations, and governments. This practice is aimed at conserving the biophysical environment from degradation and where possible repairing damage and reversing the trend. Maintaining a balanced nature grows, develops, and nourishes living things in the globe as well as achieving a healthy environment is crucial (Okezie *et al.*, 2019). Thus, environmental protection costs cover the cost of planning, controlling, utilizing, preserving, supervising, enacting, and reviewing laws that systematically integrate efforts to preserve environmental functions and prevent destruction (Adediran & Alade, 2013).

In the conduct of business operations, employees are exposed to environmental pollution and other environmental health-related challenges. Thus, companies are expected to make provisions for the protection of human lives, avoidance of accidents, and prevention of all forms of disability within the environment. Employee health and safety is a significant consideration for companies, reflecting their

commitment to sustainable and responsible operations in the midst of environmental and safety challenges. Thus, Chinedu *et al.* (2019) defined employee health and safety cost as the amount of resources expended in caring for the safety and health of the workers, including the cost of securing the working environment.

Since the industrial revolution, greenhouse gas emissions, especially carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, have caused climate change. Thus, corporate stakeholders are conscious of the management of climate change risks and demand remedial actions from the firms. In the fight against climate change, firms provide remedial measures about what they do to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and the number of emissions over the years. Thus, the concept of gas emission cost was defined by Okere *et al.* (2022) as the cost of reduction or elimination of carbon dioxide pollutants at their sources. It includes the cost of avoiding, managing, treating, disposal, or cleaning up a pollutant. Firms adopt activities such as redesigning machines to cause less pollution during manufacturing, use, or disposal and altering production processes to minimize the use of toxic chemicals, implementing better housekeeping practices to minimize leaks and fugitive releases from manufacturing processes, and taking steps to reduce energy consumption.

Empirical Review

In order to establish the statistical impact of environmental costs on the value of firms, studies were conducted in different countries using different industries, methodologies, and the period covered. Thus, some of these studies are reviewed under this section in order to establish gaps that this study intended to fill in. Ezenwaka *et al.* (2022) examined the effect of pollution costs and employees' health and safety costs on the financial performance of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria. Panel regression analysis was used to analyze the data collected from annual reports and accounts for the period of ten years (2011-2020). The study reported a positive and significant effect of pollution management costs and employees' health and safety costs on the financial performance of the companies. Likewise the study of Aniefor *et al.* (2023) on the effect of carbon emission management cost on the financial performance of 7 oil and gas companies in Nigeria. Using secondary data obtained from annual reports and accounts for the year 2023 and OLS for the analysis of data; the study also reported a positive and significant effect of carbon emission management cost on the financial performance of the firms. This was further confirmed by the study of Darlington and Cecilia (2023) on the effect of carbon emission cost on the financial performance of Nigerian listed oil and gas companies.

Data was collected from annual reports and accounts and was analyzed using regression analysis. The study also reported a positive and significant effect of emissions costs on the financial performance of the companies. However, the study of Eric and Jacob (2022) on the impact of waste management costs on the financial performance of quoted oil companies revealed a negative effect of waste management costs on the financial performance of the companies. To achieve this, the study used secondary data obtained from annual reports and accounts of the companies for ten years and were analyzed using regression analysis. This result was also confirmed by the study of Ilelaboya and Alade (2022) on the relationship between environmental accounting and the financial performance of family-owned companies listed on the Nigerian stock exchange. Data was collected from annual reports and accounts of the companies for nine years (2012-2020) and was analyzed using regression analysis. The study reported a negative insignificant relationship between environmental cost and financial performance, while employees' health and safety cost shows a positive insignificant effect on the financial performance of the companies. More so, Desai and Raval (2022) confirmed this result by examining the relationship between market value and CO₂ emission of listed firms in India. Data was also obtained from annual reports and accounts of the companies and were

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analyzed using regression analysis. The study reported a significantly negative impact of CO₂ emission cost on the value of the companies over the period of the study.

On a different note, Adeneyi and Adebayo (2020) conducted a study on green management costs and financial performance of thirteen listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. The data obtained from the financial reports and accounts of the selected company for the year 2018 was analyzed using panel linear regression analysis and the result revealed no significant effect of environmental protection cost on the profitability of the companies. In his study, Steve (2020) evaluated the effect of environmental costs on the performance of sixty-four listed industrial companies in four Sub-Saharan countries. The data obtained from annual reports and accounts of the companies for a ten-year period (2007-2016) was analyzed using panel regression analysis and the result revealed that environmental costs proxies by employee health and safety cost, waste management, and community development costs have no significant effect on return on capital employed, earnings per share and return on equity of the companies. This result was further buttressed by the study of Eke *et al.* (2024) on the effect of employees' health and safety costs on the profitability of 4 listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria. The data collected from annual reports and accounts were analyzed using panel

regression analysis and the result shows no significant effect of employee health and safety costs on profitability of the companies.

Looking at the studies reviewed, it is clear that, there are limited studies on the concepts of environmental costs and firm's value. More so, most of the studies concentrated on oil and gas companies with less attention given to other sectors that are also environmentally sensitive such as manufacturing companies. Furthermore, the previous studies reported contradictory results, hence inconclusive. Thus, the motivation of this study is to adopt manufacturing companies in Nigeria and observe the impact of environmental costs on the value of the companies over a period of 10 years (2014-2023). This would add to the body of knowledge since the study adopted listed manufacturing companies that were less considered in the previous studies and the time period covered would also reveal the consistency of environmental management practices of these companies while using a comprehensive proxy of environmental costs.

Theoretical Review

Several theories such as agency theory, legitimacy theory, and stakeholders' theory were used by previous studies to explain the concepts of environmental accounting and firms' performance. However, Henry (2001) was of the opinion that the stakeholders'

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theory is the most appropriate theory to explain the concept of environmental accounting, as the theory explains the essence of corporate environmental activities. Thus, stakeholders' theory is adopted as a theoretical base for this study.

Stakeholder theory was employed in accounting literature to provide a justification for corporate social and environmental practices. The theory discusses the recognition and identification of various stakeholders that relate to the firm (Eke *et al.*, 2024). The theory emphasizes that, for a firm to continue to exist, it requires the support of the stakeholders. Hence, the firm must adjust to gain its legitimacy through stakeholders' acceptable behaviour. The more powerful the stakeholders the more the company must adapt (Kamal, 2012). Despite the number of stakeholders, firms owe them accountability. Thus, (Gacar, 2016) emphasized that the more important the stakeholder to the organization, the more effort will be made to manage and manipulate this relationship.

With respect to environmental accounting practices, it can be observed that stakeholder theory explains the relationships in the real world based on its descriptive aspect (Harjoto *et al.*, 2015). Based on the idea of stakeholder theory, corporate environmental accounting is regarded as a means by which stakeholders are managed to gain support and approval for the organization's

continued existence (Jain & Jamali, 2016) as well as to distract stakeholders' opposition and disapproval (Boulouta, 2013). Since various stakeholders are demanding more environmental consciousness due to their interest in environmental issues and their related costs and liabilities (Adams *et al.*, 2011), organizations are engaging in various environmental activities apart from their traditional business activities to gain stakeholders' approval. Environmental issues are taken into consideration by stakeholders' risk and return. Thus, stakeholders' increasing demand for corporate environmental activities necessitates companies to show their past and future environmentally friendly activities such as waste management, gas emission management, employees' health and safety, and ecological management. Therefore, developing stakeholder theory provides a structure for the environmental issues of the relationship between stakeholders and business corporations. Hence, this study believed that stakeholder theory is appropriate to serve as a basis for the evaluation of the effect of environmental costs on the financial performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Method

This study adopted a correlation research design to define the structure and strategy of the study. The target population consisted of all the listed manufacturing companies on

the main board of the Nigerian Exchange Group as of 31st December 2023 and were forty-three (43) in number. Out of the 43 companies, 16 were selected as samples based on the criteria that; the selected companies must have been listed on or before 31st December 2013 and remained listed till 2023; and also the selected companies were active in terms of environmental reporting within the period of the study evidenced with the inclusion of environmental disclosure in their annual report and accounts over the period of ten years (2014-2023). The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics and panel regression analysis.

A panel regression model was developed in line with the model used by Ubesie *et al* (2022). The Model was developed to

evaluate the impact of environmental costs (WMC, EMC, EHC, GEC) on the value (FMV) of the companies while controlling firms' characteristics (FMS, FML). Thus, the model is presented as follows.

$$Y = F(WMC, EMC, EHC, GEC, FMS, FML) \dots\dots\dots \text{equation}$$

$$FMV_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 WMC_{it} + \beta_2 EMC_{it} + \beta_3 EHC_{it} + \beta_4 GEC_{it} + \beta_5 FMS_{it} + \beta_6 FML_{it} + \mu_{it} \dots\dots\dots \text{model 1}$$

Table 1 presents study variables which gives information with respect to the measurement

of the concepts of the study as used by previous studies.

Table 1: *Variables identification and measurement*

Label	Variable	Description	Sources
FMV	Firms value	Tobin's Q = (Market value of outstanding shares + Total Liabilities + Inventory)- Current assets divided by Total Assets.	Reschiwati <i>et al.</i> , 2020
WMC	Waste management cost	Natural logarithms of the expenses or cost of waste management for a year	Okere <i>et al.</i> , 2022
EMC	Ecological management cost	Natural logarithms of the expenses of eco-friendly management	Lawrence & Bernard, 2023
EHC	Employee health and safety cost	Natural logarithms of the expenses or cost of employee health and safety for a year	Chinedu <i>et al.</i> , 2023
GEC	Gas emission management cost	Natural logarithms of the expenses or cost of gas emission control for a year	Jones <i>et al.</i> , 2023
FMS	Firms size	Natural logarithms of total assets	Jin & Xu, 2020
FML	Firms' leverage	Debt to equity ratio for a year	Eke <i>et al.</i> , 2024

Results and Discussions

The results of descriptive statistics are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: *Descriptive statistics*

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	Min.	Max.
FMV	.1922	.1282	.0038	.3977
WMC	.0341	.0506	.0001	.1961
EMC	.0671	.1540	.0025	.5551
EHC	.0827	.0514	.0015	.2333
GEC	.1617	.2183	.0074	.7192
FMS	14.469	1.738	9.170	20.850
FML	.1330	.1172	.0201	.5400

Source: STATA 14 Output (2024)

Table 2 shows that firms value (FMV) has an average value of .1922, a standard deviation of .1282, and minimum and maximum values of .0038 and .3977 respectively. Waste management cost has a mean value of .0341 that falls in between a minimum value of .0001 and a maximum value of .1961 with a standard deviation of .0506. More so, ecological management cost has a mean of .0671, standard deviation of .1540, minimum value of .0025, and maximum value of .5551. Employee health and safety cost shows a mean value of .0827

with a standard deviation of .0514, minimum value of .0015, and maximum value of .2333. Furthermore, gas emission management cost revealed an average value of .1617 that falls in between a minimum value of .0074 and a maximum value of .7192 with a standard deviation of .2183. Looking at the values of descriptive statistics, the data collected are partially dispersed. Furthermore, correlation analysis was carried out using Pearson moment correlation statistics and the results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: *Correlation Results*

Variables	FMV	WMC	EMC	EHC	GEC	FMS	FML
FMV	1						
WMC	-.2631	1					
EMC	.0133	-.2101	1				
EHC	.0382	.1279	.2838	1			
GEC	.3017	-.2368	-.3034	.2133	1		
FMS	.2844	.7108	.5291	.4122	.3223	1	
FML	.1002	-.1312	.0460	-.0103	-.0614	-.1415	1

Source: STATA 14 Output (2024)@5%

To conduct a regression analysis, the data collected must satisfy the assumption of regression analysis such as the normality of the data collected, the absence of

multicollinearity, and autocorrelation. Thus, the result of this analysis is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: *Diagnostic test results*

Variables	VIF	1/VIF	Std. Skewness	Std. Kurtosis
WMC	2.8794	0.3473	.1322	4.7121
EMC	4.6119	0.2168	.4184	5.9266
EHC	3.7494	0.2667	.4657	6.6854
GEC	3.3240	0.3008	-.0680	5.2542
FMS	3.2934	0.3036	.3091	7.6122
FML	1.2500	0.7901	.5740	4.9969

Hausman test = .0000
Durbin Watson test = 1.3174 Chi² pro. .0000

Source: STATA 14 Output (2024)

Table 4 shows that the absolute skewness values were all less than 1.96, and kurtosis more than 3. Hence, the data is considered to be moderately skewed and platy Kurtic (Gujarati, 2008). The variance inflation factor (VIF) shows a maximum value of 4.6119 with a minimum value of 1.2500, while the maximum tolerance coefficient is 0.7901 with a minimum value of 0.2168. Thus, the data are normally distributed and

have no multicollinearity problem (Hair *et al.*, 2014). Hausman model specification test of 0.000 is also significant, thus, the null hypothesis was rejected (random effect) in favour of fixed effect.

Given the normally distributed data and no issues of multicollinearity and autocorrelation, panel regression analysis was carried out and the results are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: *Regression results*

Variables	Coeff.	p-value
Constant	.5132	.0014
WMC	-.6930	.0355
EMC	.2263	.0053
EHC	.2827	.0293
GEC	.2318	.0016
FMS	.3105	.7123
FML	.1716	.2690

R² = .6072
Adj. R² = .5084
Wald Chi² = 132, p < .0000

Source: STATA 14 Output (2024)

Table 5 revealed R² of .6072 and Adjusted R² of .5084 meaning the variables in the model accounted for 60.72% of the variation in the value of the companies, while 39.28% could be explained by other factors. The model as a whole was found to be significant given an intercept p-value of .0401 at a 5%

level of significant and Wald Chi² of 132 with a p-value of .0000 indicating the goodness of fit and the validity of the model. Table 5 further shows that waste management cost has a negative but significant ($\beta = -.6930$; $p = .0355$) impact on the value of the companies at a 5% level of

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significance. This implies that an increase in waste management costs will result in a significant decrease in the value of the companies. Furthermore, the negative but significant effect of waste management costs on Tobin's Q implies that firms' expenses on waste management could not attract investors, because higher waste management cost shows the company cannot maximize its profit, leading the investor to release shares off the market and lower the share price. Thus, the conclusion is that waste management cost has a negative significant impact on the value of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria over the period of the study. This result corroborated studies such as Eric and Jacob (2022) and Ilelaboya and Alade (2022) that also reported a negative relationship between waste management costs and financial performance. However, this contradicted the results of studies such as Steven (2020) which reported an insignificant effect of waste management cost on financial performance.

However, Ecological management costs were found to have a positive and significant ($\beta = .2263$; $p = .0053$) impact on the value of the companies. This means that an increase in ecological management costs would significantly increase the value of the companies. Thus, the conclusion is that ecological management costs have a positive and significant impact on the value of the companies. Furthermore, employee

health and safety cost shows positive and significant ($\beta = .2827$; $p = .0293$) impact on the value of the companies. This implies that an increase in employee health and safety costs would increase the value of the companies. Thus emphasizing the need for management to pay adequate attention to policies that will reduce employee exposure to pollution, accident, and protection of human lives. It confirmed the results of the previous studies such as Ezenwaka *et al.* (2022) and Ilelaboya and Alade (2022) that also reported a positive and significant effect of employees' health and safety cost on the firm's value. However, it contradicted studies such as Eke *et al.* (2024), and Steve (2020) which documented an insignificant impact of employee health and safety costs on firms' performance. With respect to gas emission management cost, Table 5 shows positive and significant ($\beta = .2318$; $p = .0016$) impact of gas emission management cost on the value of the companies at a 5% level of significance. This implies that increasing firms' attention on activities such as avoiding, managing, treating, disposal, or cleaning up a pollutant would significantly attract investors to invest in the companies, hence improving firms' value. Thus, the conclusion is gas emission management cost has a positive and significant impact on the value of companies. This result confirmed studies of Aniefor *et al.* (2023), Darlington and Cecilia (2023) who also reported positive and significant impact of carbon

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emission management cost on firm performance. However, it contradicts studies such as Desai and Rayal (2022) and Adeniyi and Adebayo (2020) who documented the negative and insignificant impact of gas emission management cost on firm value.

The positive and significant impact of ecological management cost, employees' health and safety cost, and gas emissions management cost on Tobin's Q further meant that higher environmental cost on these variables leads to higher market reaction as valued significantly by investors as an expected expense. Thus, the listed manufacturing companies could use this to attract investors with high-profit returns and minimal cost.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The findings of this study, reveal that ecological management costs, employee health and safety costs, and gas emission management costs have positive and significant impacts on Tobin's Q ratio of companies, while waste management cost shows negative and significant impact on Tobin's Q ratio of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria over the period of the study. Therefore, the study concluded that environmental cost has a positive and significant impact on the value of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. This implies that improving environmental management systems such as ecological

management, employee health and safety, and gas emission management will significantly improve firms' value through increased share market prices.

Therefore, this study recommends that the management of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria should pay adequate attention to policies such as conserving the biophysical environment from degradation, maintaining a balanced natural growth, reducing employees' exposure to pollution, and work accidents, providing health insurance, installing modern equipment for waste collection and disposal, and adoption of eco-friendly production process. This would help management to gain trust from both employees and the operating community, hence improving firms' value through an increase in share price and product market price.

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